

Socio-Economic Factors behind Migration: A Case of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT:

The primary cause of the fast urbanization is the migration of people from rural to urban regions. In this study, individual migratory patterns were investigated in a socioeconomic setting. The purpose of the study was to shed light on how individuals migrate in response to shifting socioeconomic and demographic trends. The current study was carried out in Islamabad, one of Pakistan's metropolitan districts. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The only respondents included in this research were those who moved from rural to urban areas and began a family at least three years ago. Information was gathered on socioeconomic factors, such as age, work, health facilities, family income, and literacy. In addition, inquiries were made concerning their reasons for relocating, push and pull factors, and viewpoints on urbanization and its effects. The data analysis was done using the relevant statistical methods. The migratory behavior of most respondents is found to be mostly affected by "Pull Factors," with sixty-six percent of them being drawn to cities in search of a "better lifestyle." Three socioeconomic factors, age, income, and education, were shown to have the most effects on the respondents' attitudes regarding migration.

KEY WORDS:

Migration, Socio-Economic, Occupation, Pull Factors, Urbanization

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Introduction

It is in everyone's nature to both meet and beyond expectations. Humans migrate in an effort to make the most of their social and physical settings. The most complex processes are those related to migration, mortality, and fertility. The mass exodus of people from rural areas into densely populated metropolitan centers is the primary problem facing governments in the world's less developed regions. Any prolonged, indefinite relocation is called a "migration." It involves "organizing activities at one place and moving from the overall round of activities to another location (Martin, [2014](#)).

With the rising interconnectedness of the world, migration is becoming a major global phenomenon. Many variables impact the choice to move, but socioeconomic reasons are the most important ones. The public, politicians, and academics all need to be aware of the complex linkages that exist between these factors and migratory trends. This research will examine the different ways that economic, social, and demographic elements come together to form the complex web of human mobility in order to gain a better understanding of the relationship between migration and socioeconomic characteristics. As we continue our investigation, it becomes clear that understanding the intricacies of migration necessitates a careful examination of the forces that propel people and groups to travel across borders in quest of better lives (Farah et al., [2012](#)).

Socioeconomic consideration is one of the many aspects impacting the intricate phenomenon of migration patterns. This article explores in detail how migration trends are influenced by socioeconomic considerations. Migration trends are significantly influenced by socioeconomic considerations. The main motivators are the pay scale in the targeted locations, the status of the economy, and the availability of jobs. Healthcare, education, and overall quality of life all have an influence on moving decisions. On the other hand, negative economic conditions, a lack of job possibilities, and insufficient living standards often cause people to leave their home country in pursuit of better chances. Social networks, cultural ties, and government policies also play roles in shaping migration dynamics (Odey, [2018](#)).

Economics Disparities

Unemployment is a primary cause of migration. Families and individuals frequently move to areas with greater employment possibilities, salary rates, and general economic stability in search of better economic chances.

Education and Skills Migration

Migration is prompted by the need for specialized skills and high-quality education. Individuals may relocate to places with well-known academic institutions or thriving enterprises related to their fields of expertise, fostering economic growth and knowledge exchange.

Trends in Employment and Jobs Markets

Migration is greatly impacted by changes in employment patterns and job markets. Areas with thriving sectors draw workforces, influencing migration patterns, whereas regions going through economic downturns may see an increase in out-migration.

The affordability of housing and the cost of living are two major determinants of people's migration decisions. Exodus from expensive metropolitan regions may occur, while migration to more affordable places is attracted (Najjarkakhaki & Ghane, [2023](#)).

Healthcare Accessibility

The standard and accessibility of medical services affect migration trends. People migrating to areas with better healthcare systems may have an impact on migration pattern, especially during time off global health emergencies (Dustmann et al., [2007](#)).

Overall Objectives

The study was designed to know the factors responsible for shaping migration attitude in the socio-economic context. To look into how migration is affected by socioeconomic factors.

Review of Literature

A summary of previously published works on a particular subject is called a literature review. The phrase can be used to describe the whole publication or just a certain portion of a book, essay, or other intellectual work. Either way, a literature review's main goal is to provide the reader and the researcher/author with a thorough understanding of the body of previous studies on the subject at hand.

The "Push-Pull Theory," which maintains that some individuals migrate because they are compelled to leave their previous area while others migrate because they are pushed or pulled to a new site, is the most widely accepted explanation of migration across time. The first person to propose this idea was the migration expert Ravenstein (1889) in England. Pull factors, in his opinion, are more significant than push forces. Better and more appealing living conditions are "pull" factors, whereas less desirable living conditions are "push" factors, in Jakson's opinion. He believes that "better opportunities at the place of destination are pull factors, and declining socio-economic

conditions at the place of origin are push factors (Hugo, 2005). The allure of "city lights" was shown to be unimportant in studies of immigration to various Asian cities: economic hardship in varying degrees was the real reason for practically all migration. Migration has a direct effect on the areas that migrants move to, the places they leave behind, and the migrants themselves. Migration alters the social, economic, and demographic makeup of both groups, which affects the pace of population increase in each place. One of the largest demographic shifts in human history is the fast urbanization or the migration of people from rural to urban areas. This trend is at least as important to the world as the "explosion" of population. Migration from rural to urban areas contributes to the nation's growing unemployment rate, crowded cities, inefficiencies, and development imbalances (Hashim et al., 2021). Generally speaking, it appears that the effects of having a higher quality of life in urban areas as opposed to rural ones are the easiest to identify. Urban regions provide distinct social and economic prospects, yet residents frequently balance these benefits against one of the most well-known drawbacks of growing urbanization and traffic. There's no denying that living in a densely populated area has negative effects. There is an increase in mortality due to living in filthy, unhygienic homes. Cities are typically associated with crime and depravity. Based on the results of the population census conducted in 1998, the percentage of people residing in rural Pakistan decreased by 4.2%, from 71.7% in 1981 to 67.5% in 1998. Consequently, the percentage of people living in cities grew by 4.2%, from 28.3% in 1981 to 32.5% in 1998. This implies that a third of the population now resides in the town or city. In every province, the population living in urban areas has grown while those living in rural regions have declined (Hassan et al., 2021). However, many of these immigrants lack even the most basic urban facilities, such as access to water, sewage, garbage collection, medical care, education, security, housing, transportation, and power, as a result of the strain that rising populations impose on cities. Because of this, people find it difficult to adapt, and they also cause issues for other people and urban planners. Unemployment is more pronounced in the city since there are more skilled and unskilled workers than there are open positions. In order to address the housing shortage, migrants erect unauthorized encampments on public property and construct their own homes out of whatever materials they can find. According to Wang et al. (2019), these squatter areas impede the easy flow of traffic and provide harmful circumstances that contaminate the environment.

Research Methodology

The methodological steps taken in this research are presented in the figure and diagrammatically.

Study Area

Islamabad is the largest city in Pakistan, with a population of just over 2 million (Population Census Organization). The present study was conducted in Islamabad, Pakistan. Respondents were selected purposively who were migrated to Islamabad, Pakistan.

Study Population

In this research study, fifty male heads of migrant families comprised the sample. The method of purposeful sampling was used to choose the respondents. In this study, a migrant is limited to males who moved from rural to urban areas at least three years ago and had a family.

Data Collection & Analysis

An interview schedule was created to investigate the study goals. The interview agenda contained primarily planned questions. The questionnaire was pre-tested before the actual application to ensure its validity and suitability for use, and any required modifications were made. Information was gathered on socioeconomic factors such as health facilities, age, occupation, family income, and literacy. In addition, inquiries concerning their reason for migrating, driving forces (push and pull factors), and views on urbanization and its effects were made. The data thus collected were analyzed in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to arrive at a logical conclusion.

Results and Discussion

Table number 1 depicts that minimum age of the selected respondents was 21 years with maximum age of 72 years. Literacy rate in the selected sample size was very low as results described that minimum education was four years of education and maximum of 18 years of education. While in the respondents most of the respondents' education was above matric level, few respondents had an education less than matric, but one thing was important: they were fully aware of their issues. That's why most of the family choices were made by these individuals since they were mindful of reality. They had good knowledge of their problems and their solutions. That's why mostly decided migration to cities to solve their problems and to make better future for their children. Table. 1

Table 1

Statistics with respect to age and education

	N	Minimum	Maximum
Age (years)	50	21	72
Education (years)	50	04	16

Source: Field Survey, 2024

As per data collection, five respondents said they were living alone after migration; actually, they were here to earn money so they could support their families back in their areas, while majority 38 respondents said that they are living in a Nuclear family after migration, after more discussion they said they moved here to support their children education, to provide better facilities to their children that's why they move and to compete the real world, same like this 07 respondents were living in a joint family which is defined as families with members who are related by blood and who have lived together under one roof and worked under a common head for several generations. While between them seven respondents were working as a labor to support their families while, 17 were running their own business and mostly 26 said they are doing jobs in different sector. Table. 2

Table 2

Socio-economic statistics

Alone	Family Type		Labor Work	Occupation	
	Nuclear Family	Joint Family		Business	Job
05	38	7	07	17	26

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The majority of the population in the villages was devoid of decent living circumstances and the necessities of life, according to the research findings. Therefore, a significant portion of the respondents' movement behavior was shaped by the "Pull factors." They chose to move regardless of the expense since they were drawn to city living. A little over 48% of respondents said they moved to the city in search of work. The primary stimulants that inspired the majority of responders were pull forces. While push factors play a smaller role in encouraging respondents to

migrate. A large majority of respondents were extremely stimulated by pull factors. The "lack of educational opportunities and better Living Standard were the most potential socioeconomic push factors. Table. 3

Table 3

Social factors responsible for migration to cities

	Push Factors		Pull Factors	
	N	%	N	%
To some extent	24	48	17	34
To greater extent	15	30	33	66
No at all	11	22	00	00

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table As peer research, 62% of the respondents, or a large majority, were fully aware of the negative effects of migration into cities. The majority of respondents said that they were facing serious concerns about unemployment in that city. While 42% strongly favoring poor social service provision, it was considered the second significant concern. Environmental contamination was ranked as another significant issue by 42 percent of respondents. So, major issues were highlighted by the targeted population in selected areas. Due to the high rate of migration in cities, there have been a lot of social issues since then. For the prevention of these issues, the government must take some actions to stop these migrants by providing them with basic facilities in their own town or by working on these social problems so every individual can live a better life. Table. 4

Table 4

Social problems faced by individuals in migrated city

Problem	To Greater extent		To some extent		Not at all	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Unemployment	31	62	14	28	05	10
Contamination of environment	21	42	26	52	03	06
Sanitation issues	13	26	17	34	20	40
Poor provision of Social Services	21	42	16	32	13	26
Inadequate Housing	08	16	11	22	31	62

Source: Field Survey, 2024

In this table, mostly migrants were happy after moving to cities they were saying they have changed their life style, their thinking, their way of communication is totally changed. Now they are much improved to face different challenges in lives. They were satisfied with their daily life and the provision of different social facilities. Here, thirty-nine percent of respondents were satisfied about their children's future. Most people were saying after moving to the city, their mindset has totally changed. Now, they also have some savings to combat unannounced problems. So, as per the results, it can be imagined that most people were happy to move here and they were improving in every sphere of life. They were working for their families, and in this regard, they were getting positive results. Although there were some issues, in the end, they were achieving their goals. Table. 5

Table 5

Impact of migration on life cycle

Status	Better	Same	Worse
Life Style	29	16	05
Food Quality	28	20	02

Status	Better	Same	Worse
Health facilities/Household needs	37	09	04
Feeling about Children Lives	39	06	05
Ownership of Assets	25	24	01
Savings	27	23	00
Overall Condition	36	08	06

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Conclusion and Recommendations

The survey's results allow us to conclude that respondents' opinions regarding migration were predominantly influenced by their age, income, and educational attainment, among other socioeconomic criteria. Young folks with large families, no formal education, and limited job experience, made up the majority of the commenters. Before moving, the majority of them were regarded as low-income individuals from a financial standpoint. Most of them relocated in pursuit of higher wages, more educational opportunities, and better living circumstances. Published in 1889, Ravenstein developed the "Push-Pull Theory," which holds that some individuals migrate because they are compelled to leave their current location, while others migrate because they are attracted to or lured to a new one. The investigation's results validated this theory. The results of this survey show that pull factors were the main sources of motivation for most respondents. Pull factors had a greater influence on the majority of respondents than push factors did on their migration decisions. In 1956, UNESCO declared that "economic hardship in varying degrees was the real reason for practically all migrations" in an attempt to determine the true cause of rural-urban migration. The results of the current studies corroborated this assertion, with most of the respondents moving to the city in search of employment and then in search of a higher standard of living; also, many were moving in search of better educational opportunities.

Migration from rural to urban areas is a contributing factor to the country's growing unemployment rate, urban traffic jams, inefficiencies, and imbalances in development. Kuznets (1964). The results clearly show that the high pace of migration has led to a number of issues with city living, including unemployment, inadequate social services, environmental damage, and the issue of migrant housing. Although most people believe they were having a better life in the village, they are also fully aware of these factors. However, despite the fantastic facilities offered in the villages, people are still not ready to return because of the fast-paced nature of migration. A significant correlation was shown between the respondents' age and their views on migration. According to data, young adults are more mobile than persons of other ages, suggesting that age and migratory attitude are strongly correlated. The findings demonstrate the range of opinions held by respondents from various socioeconomic backgrounds. Regarding income levels, the respondents' priorities are different. The majority of the low-income group's respondents moved in search of work because they wanted to boost their income. While the high-income respondents had moved to better their lifestyle, the mediocre respondents' primary goal was to improve their educational capacities; they all were very serious about their future generation as well.

There will always be a migration from rural to urban areas—it cannot be stopped. Still, there is a way to reduce the pressure on individuals to move into cities. The following recommendations, which take into account the research findings, might aid in the creation of a sensible and practical immigration policy:

- ▶ It should go without saying that most individuals leave their communities because they are unable to lead happy lives. As a result, in order to fund the necessities of a contemporary, comfortable living, the government must set aside a higher proportion of development expenditures. The horrible circumstances that now exist in our rural areas, including those related to recreation, roads, transit, health, and nutrition, should be improved and enhanced.

- ▶ Because of the high unemployment rate in rural areas, people without jobs are driven to relocate to cities in search of better job opportunities and higher income levels. The government must provide incentives to attract investors to launch new enterprises in these industries. As a result, these regions may attract business, and the jobs that result will attract people.
- ▶ Fostering agro-based enterprises is one strategy to reduce the rate of widespread rural emigration.

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